

Prospective of Animal Taxonomy And Their Incorporation In Several Branches Of Biological Sciences

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The field I selected is Animal Taxonomy. Animal taxonomy can help us study various animal diversity, and much needed by another study of science, either from the branch of biology or others (Rosadi & Pratomo, 2010). Animal taxonomy is a basic science that can be mix with other sciences, one of which is mix with ethnobiology. As a scientific discipline, ethnobiology has not yet well-developed in Indonesia (Iskandar, J., 2016, p.27). With this merger, we can examine what animals have been using in human culture. That's why I am interested in how earlier humans used animals as a medium of treatment. Animal taxonomy is also closely related to conservation, as some animals contribute to conservation, whether environmental, plant or, animal conservation. Furthermore, in animal identification, animal taxonomy can be mix with genetics and morphology.

The use of animals as traditional medicine is still widely done in Indonesia. Parts of the animal's body usually used as folk remedies are meat, horns, bones, tails, feathers, nails, fat, bile, and shells (Nukraheni, Afriansyah, & Ihsan, 2019, p.61). The use of animals as traditional medicines comes from hereditary public beliefs. Some animals used as medicine believes to have high effectiveness in curing diseases. Some people use this knowledge to carry out traditional medicine, but some people carry out treatment without the permission of BPOM, the Food and Drug Administration (Hamdani, Herwina, & Tjong, 2013, p.112). This public knowledge can be used as an object of research because it still needs to be developed and needs proof from scientific aspects so that its utilization can inform, both in terms of truth and idolatry.

Next is a combination of animal taxonomy and conservation. According to Rachman, M. (2012), there are at least four values included in the concept of conservation, namely planting, utilizing, preserving, and studying (p.30). Between living things and the environment provide a reciprocal relationship in terms of conservation. Handru, Herwina, & Dahelmi revealed that the existence of conservation forests is an effort to maintain special ecological functions or other characteristics of the area. These include biodiversity, protection of water sources, and populations of endangered species (p70). By animal taxonomy, I want to research animals that play a role in the success of conservation. There is still a lot of research that was not related to the role of animals in conservation. Maybe research about that can make me discover new facts. That's like research by Griffiths, Asthon, Evans, Perr, & Eggleton (2019) demonstrate that termites can be responsible for most wood mass loss. Using a deadwood decomposition assay, we found termites were responsible for 58–64% of total mass loss, while microbes carried out 36–42% (p.R118).

Today the universe still holds many stories. There are still many species of species that have unidentified. I wanted to do some research with the combination of animal taxonomy, genetics, and morphology. From this, I will explore various biodiversity and identify morphological and genetic comparisons of some of the species I would later discover. environmental DNA (e-DNA) is the one method of identification with the genetic approach. e-DNA is an analytical method that used DNA sources from the environment

(water, phases, etc.), so with this method, the organism will not be disturbed. Roesma, Tjong, Janra, & Aidil,. (2021) said e-DNA has the potential to be an effective method with next-generation sequencing (NGS) that can read all DNA in parallel on one sequential process (p.2794). Morphological identification can use with a photography approach. That is like research by Janra, M. N. (2018), who conducts inventory and identification with a photographic method. Janra, M. N. (2018) said the photography approach promises an immense help in does species inventories, its reliability in determining species identification without harming species population (p.18). It is possible that from this combination, I was able to find a species that unidentified before. Such as research conducted by Sgarlata et al. in 2019 that successfully identified two new species of the genus *microcebus* (*Microcebus marohita* and *Microcebus tanosi*) found in the tropical forests in Madagascar.

By combining animal taxonomy with other fields of science, we can understand many things. For example, through combination with morphological/genetic, we can know biodiversity without must destroy organisms in a population, understanding the role of animals in conservation, and understand how traditional society can determine animals that can use as medicines.

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